

Utilization of Non-Verbal Communication in Kindergarten Instruction: Basis for an Intervention Plan

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Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in a medium-sized schools division in Northern Negros during the School Year 2024-2025 as a basis for an intervention plan. It involved 37 Kindergarten teachers who responded to the researcher-developed survey questionnaire. The purposive sample technique was employed due to the manageable total number of respondents. This study employed a descriptive research methodology. Findings showed that the demographic profile of the kindergarten teachers varies in terms of age, civil status, length of service, and plantilla position. It revealed that kindergarten teachers utilized non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the areas of hand signal, behavior temperature chart, and whistle discipline to a moderate extent. Younger and older kindergarten teachers used hand signal to a high and moderate extent respectively. Single teachers exhibited a high extent of utilization of hand signal compared to married teachers who display moderate extent. Teachers with shorter length of service had high extent on the use of hand signal while those teachers with longer length of service demonstrate a moderate extent. In terms of behavior temperature chart and whistle discipline, both groups of teachers display a moderate extent of utilization. In terms of plantilla position, teachers with lower rank exhibits a high extent of utilization of hand signal while those higher in rank garner moderate extent. Also, both groups of teachers have moderate extent on the use of behavior temperature chart. Meanwhile, teachers in lower rank have moderate extent and teachers in higher rank garners a low extent on the use of whistle development. The findings suggest that in order to further enhance classroom engagement and management, kindergarten teachers need to enhance their non-verbal communication skills in the areas of behavior temperature chart and whistle discipline through a proposed Learning and Development plan focusing on upskilling kindergarten teachers' competence on the use of non-verbal communication strategies inside the classroom.

Keywords: Non-verbal communication, hand signal, behavior temperature chart, whistle discipline

Introduction:

Nature of Problem

Information can be communicated nonverbally by using body language or facial expressions. This could entail expressing a point with particular hand or facial motions, as well as by making or not making eye contact, being close to someone, and using other nonverbal clues (Cherry, 2019). Non-verbal cues are largely used for communication. As a matter of fact, experts contend that the percentage of non-verbal communication is really four times higher than that of verbal communication, with actions and gestures accounting for 80% of human communication and words for only 20% (Hull, 2016). In the context of education, the non-verbal communication is very crucial in the classroom for it can convey significant information and cues that improve knowledge and engagement (Surkamp, 2014).

The Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), as outlined by the Department of Education-Teacher Education Council (DepEd-TEC, 2017), emphasizes the teacher's role in creating a safe, secure, fair, supportive, and inclusive learning environment. This environment must be responsive to the diversity of learners and should promote learner responsibility, engagement, and academic success. In a medium-sized schools division in Northern Negros, there is a growing recognition of the importance of both verbal and non-verbal communication in classroom instruction. While verbal communication remains the primary mode for delivering lessons, non-verbal communication is increasingly encouraged as a complementary tool to enhance clarity, engagement, and comprehension, especially among learners with diverse needs and learning styles. These practices emphasize the importance of clear communication, safety protocols, and structured routines in preschool environments (American Academy of Pediatrics, 2020).

Teachers in this division are generally aware of the benefits of using non-verbal communication and employ it alongside verbal strategies. Despite these practices, it was observed that there is no formal assessment or documentation regarding the specific types of non-verbal communication tools are used, how often these are used, the intent or purpose behind their use and whether there are differences in utilization across teacher demographics. There is limited literature focusing on the non-verbal communication strategies used by teachers especially kindergarten teachers in the Philippine context, particularly within Northern Negros. Most available studies are either

international or too generalized. Kindergarten teacher practices in non-verbal communication are often intuitive and undocumented, which makes it difficult to evaluate their impact on learning outcomes.

These observations motivated the researcher to undertake a study aimed at determining the utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in a medium size schools division in Northern Negros during the School Year 2024-2025. The researcher hopes to provide meaningful insights that will support teachers in becoming more intentional and effective in their communication practices, thereby contributing to the creation of responsive, learner-centered classrooms in line with the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. The results of the study can provide valuable insights that will help improve classroom interaction and support professional development.

Current State of Knowledge

Information can be communicated nonverbally by using body language or facial expressions. This could entail expressing a point with particular hand or facial motions, as well as by making or not making eye contact, being close to someone, and using other nonverbal clues (APA, 2018). When it comes to communicating meaning and information to others and interpreting the behavior of people around us, nonverbal communication is crucial. When examining nonverbal behaviors, it's crucial to keep in mind that group activities matter. A person can learn a lot about someone's true intentions by observing their facial expressions, tone of voice, and body language in addition to their spoken words (Cherry, 2023).

Classroom hand signals are nonverbal cues teachers and students use to communicate without speaking. These signals help manage classroom behavior, convey instructions, and ensure smooth transitions between activities. Teachers can minimize disturbances and keep control of the classroom by employing basic hand signals like an open hand to indicate silence or a thumbs up to indicate approval. Introducing hand signals effectively and ensuring they become an integral part of classroom communication requires a thoughtful approach. Teachers need to go over each hand signal's meaning with the pupils and give an example of when and how to use them. They should also give precise explanations of each signal's function along with usage examples (Boschen, 2024).

Moreover, blowing air over the lips and teeth or known as whistling to produce a high-pitched sound – often producing a 'tune' with varying music notes. Whistling is a sign of happiness or that a person needs to self-soothe and calm themselves. Whistling indicates contentment, usually, however it can also signify the desire to be pacified making it context specific. Whistling can be used in any context, but should be avoided where silence is the norm such as in a library or other situations where other people require focus and concentration. This might indicate a level of momentary stress that has arisen during a difficult task (Chris, 2014).

Furthermore, Behavior charts can be a good way to motivate students to behave well, complete tasks, remember their chores or get into a routine. When a behavior chart is followed consistently, the rewards are fair and meaningful and the goals aren't impossible to reach then behavior charts can be very good. A behavior chart is a visual way to see a child's behavioral progress. A behavior chart can be used to manage a variety of behaviors. The charts can be used to track, manage, and even reward the following types of behaviors: General behavior, completion of task, following rules and procedures, attitude and avoiding poor behaviors (Cook & Hamilton, 2023).

According to Segal (2019), body cues play a vital role in strengthening messages, in substituting verbal messages, and in complementing the verbal message being conveyed. Non-verbal language, as it is interpreted in different ways and may have different meanings, can cause miscommunication. Stuart (2016) stated that miscommunication occurs in circumstances where people are unaware of making wrong assumptions which can be caused by nonverbal language. Public speaking requires great effort to be successful. In Arriesgado's (2018) article, she stated that when it comes to presentations speakers must observe and put their body language to good use.

Theoretical Underpinnings

The study has theoretical foundation on theories about non-verbal communication. The most common theoretical framework in understanding non-verbal communication is the Brunswik (1956) lens model particularly in relation to studying interpersonal judgments. The Brunswik lens model includes three components: a measured construct in a sender (such as a personality trait), (b) the sender's non-verbal behavior, and (c) the perceiver's impression of the sender on the construct (Hall, Horgan, & Murphy, 2019). Through ubiquitous verbal and nonverbal relational messages, people reciprocally signal the nature of their interpersonal relationships. Implicit signals express how people regard one another and how they gauge the ongoing status of their interpersonal relationships (Guerrero et al., 2017).

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in a medium-sized schools division in Northern Negros during the School Year 2024-2025 as a basis for an intervention plan. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the profile of the Kindergarten teachers in terms of the following variables: Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Plantilla Position (2)What is the extent

of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the following areas: Hand signal, Behavior Temperature Chart, and Whistle discipline (3) What is the extent of non-verbal communication when grouped according to their profile variables?(4)Is there a significant difference in the utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables?(5)Based on the study, what intervention can be formulated?

Methodology:

This section delineates the methodologies employed in collecting data from the respondents. The components encompass research design, study locale, respondents, data collection instrument, validity and reliability of the research instrument, data collection method, analytical frameworks, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research methodology to assess the extent of non-verbal communication utilization for kindergarten learners in a medium-sized school division in Northern Negros during the School Year 2024-2025. Descriptive design is suitable for investigations that seek to ascertain current conditions or relationships, prevailing ideas and beliefs, processes and impacts, and emerging trends. The design is a scientific approach that entails studying and delineating the behavior of a subject without any interference (Cohiggan, 2018).

Study Respondents

This study involved 37 Kindergarten teachers employed in a medium-sized school division in Northern Negros during the 2024-2025 academic year. The teachers responded to the researcher-developed survey questionnaire. The purposive sample technique was employed due to the manageable total number of respondents. Norton (2018) defines purposive sampling as a category of probability sampling methods wherein units are chosen based on the specific features required for the sample.

Instrument

This study employed a researcher-developed survey questionnaire to collect data from the respondents. This tool facilitated the efficient examination and classification of ideas. The research instrument comprised two primary components: Part I collected the demographic profiles of the respondents, including age, civil status, plantilla position, and length in service. Part II consisted of a 30-item survey, with 10 items allocated to each category: hand signal, temperature behavior chart, and whistle development. The questionnaire employed a five-point Likert scale, with the subsequent scores: 5 – Always; 4 – Frequently; 3 – Occasionally; 2 – Seldom; and 1 – Almost never. The validity assessment of the instrument resulted in a mean score of 4.96, classified as excellent. This indicates that a researcher-developed questionnaire is deemed valid. The reliability assessment of the questionnaire achieved an alpha of 0.965, classified as Excellent, signifying its reliability.

Data Gathering Procedure

The study utilized a descriptive research design wherein a survey was conducted to gather data from the respondents. For the smoother conduct of the study, a letter was sent to the Schools Division Superintendent requesting permission to conduct the study, and it was submitted for approval. After securing the approval for the request, the researcher seeks informed consent from the identified respondents. Upon approval of the respondents, the link to the Google form of the electronic survey was sent to the Messenger account or Email. In contrast, a hard copy of the survey questionnaire was handed to those without internet access. The data gathered from the respondents' responses were tallied and tabulated using the appropriate statistical tools. The raw data were transformed into numerical code guided by a coding manual. This allowed computer processing, statistical derivations, and tabular presentation. The Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to process the encoded data on the computer.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

For objective 1, descriptive analysis such as frequency and percentage distribution were utilized to ascertain the respondents' profiles about age, marital status, duration of service, and plantilla position. For objective 2, a descriptive analytical scheme such as mean and standard deviation were employed to assess the extent of non-verbal communication utilization among kindergarten learners, specifically regarding hand signals, behavior temperature charts, and whistle development. For objective 3, a descriptive analytical scheme such as mean and standard deviation were utilized to assess the extent of non-verbal communication categorized by the previously indicated characteristics. For objective 4, a comparative analytical scheme such as Mann-Whitney U test was employed to ascertain the major differences in the extent of non-verbal communication utilization among kindergarten learners, categorized and contrasted based on the specified criteria.

Ethical Considerations

The study ethics process guarantees the protection of human rights and assures that the research done is devoid of any concealed motives (Fleming, 2018). The researcher underscored the respondents' voluntary participation, informed consent, risk of damage, confidentiality, and anonymity to safeguard the study's participants. In this study, voluntary participation required respondents to sign or agree to a permission form by entering their initials or pseudonym in a designated space. Nonetheless, they had the liberty to withdraw at any moment without justification. The research guaranteed that respondents were thoroughly apprised of the processes and dangers associated with the study and were required to provide consent for participation. To mitigate the risk of injury, the researcher ensured that participants were not placed in situations that could jeopardize their safety due to their involvement. Participants may refuse to answer any questions and withdraw their participation at any time if this occurs. To ensure secrecy, the researcher assured that the participants' identifying information would be inaccessible to anybody not directly engaged in the study. Additionally, to preserve the anonymity of the respondents, they employed aliases or initials to conceal their names from the researcher and other participants.

Results and Discussions:

Table 2
Profile of Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 36 years old)	19	51.35
	Older (36-65 years old)	18	48.65
	Total	37	100
Civil Status	Single	9	24.32
	Married	28	75.68
	Total	37	100
Length of Service	Shorter (less than 9 years)	17	45.95
	Longer (9 years and more)	20	54.05
	Total	37	100
Plantilla Position	Lower (Teacher I and II)	24	64.86
	Higher (Teacher III)	13	35.14
	Total	37	100

Table 2 shows the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Plantilla Position. Results revealed that 51.35% of respondents were categorized as younger (less than 36 years old) and 48.65% as older (36 years and above). It demonstrates that the respondent's profile reflects an almost equal distribution with respect to age and length of service. Similar results are found in the study of Diaz (2024), showing that both younger (21–30 years old) and older (31–40 years old) teachers have almost equal distribution. In terms of civil status, 24.32% of the respondents were single, while 75.68% of them were married. This suggests that majority of the kindergarten teachers were married. The result supports the finding of Diaz (2024), which reveals that the majority of teachers were married, reflecting additional responsibilities and the need for work-life balance. In a similar manner, 45.95% of the respondents have been employed for less than nine years, while 54.05% have been employed for nine years or more. This is aligned with the findings of Cadampog, Cabanero, and Daing (2021), which found out in their study that most of the kindergarten teachers had teaching experience in teaching kindergarten from 1 to 5 years. This suggests that the majority of the kindergarten teachers are beginning teachers. A sizable percentage (64.8%) of plantillas were in lesser positions (Teacher I and II), whereas 35.14% were in higher ones (Teacher III). This implies that the majority of the respondents were in their early or mid-career phases. Similar results are revealed in the study of Cadampog, Cabanero, and Daing (2021), stating that most kindergarten teachers were Teacher 1 and only one teacher was Master Teacher 1.

Table 3
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Hand Signal

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...		
1. use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen.	3.65	High Extent
2. use hand signals to require silence.	3.73	High Extent
3. use hand signals to calm down or take a breath.	3.38	Moderate Extent
4. use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers.	3.49	Moderate Extent
5. use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly.	3.73	High Extent

6. use hand signals to ask preschoolers to listen more carefully.	3.49	Moderate Extent
7. use hand signals to line up.	3.35	Moderate Extent
8. use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson.	3.24	Moderate Extent
9. use hand signals to encourage quick transition.	3.32	Moderate Extent
10. use hand signals to indicate slow down.	3.73	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.51	High Extent

Table 3 shows that the overall mean was 3.51, interpreted as "high extent." Items no. 2, 5, and 10, which state, "use hand signals to require silence," "use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly," and "use hand signals to indicate slow down," received the highest mean score of 3.73 and were interpreted as "high extent." On the other hand, the lowest mean score of 3.24 was recorded for item no. 8, which states "use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson." The results reveal that kindergarten teachers used hand signals less frequently when calling students' attention during a lesson. This suggests that when attempting to regain student focus mid-lesson, teachers relied less on hand signals as a nonverbal communication method. Although hand signals are commonly used in classrooms to indicate silence, give directions, or signal transitions, their use in this particular context appeared to be limited. The use of hand signals by kindergarten teachers is a well-established strategy for managing behavior and sustaining attention. The results somewhat contradict the findings of Boschen (2024), who states that hand signals facilitate effective behavior management, instructional delivery, and smooth transitions between activities. By using simple gestures. Hand signals serve as powerful nonverbal cues that support efficient classroom management.

Table 4
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior Temperature chart

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...		
1. use behavior chart to minimize noise.	3.43	Moderate Extent
2. use behavior chart to minimize standing up.	3.49	Moderate Extent
3. use behavior chart to stop bullying.	3.62	High Extent
4. use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness.	3.30	Moderate Extent
5. use behavior chart to return borrowed things.	3.27	Moderate Extent
6. use behavior chart to encourage courteous expressions.	3.46	Moderate Extent
7. use behavior chart to complete schoolwork.	3.43	Moderate Extent
8. use behavior chart to stay on task.	3.43	Moderate Extent
9. use behavior chart for positive participation.	3.27	Moderate Extent
10. use behavior chart to show responsibility of their belongings and classroom materials.	3.41	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.41	Moderate Extent

The data in table 4 show how much behavior temperature charts were used by kindergarten instructors as a nonverbal communication technique for classroom management. The overall mean of 3.41 was interpreted as "moderate extent." Item no. 3, which states "use behavior chart to stop bullying," received the highest mean score of 3.62 and was interpreted as "high extent." Meanwhile, items no. 5 and 9, which say "use behavior chart to return borrowed things" and "use behavior chart for positive participation," received the lowest mean scores of 3.27 and were both interpreted as "moderate extent." Kindergarten teachers were less likely to use behavior temperature charts to monitor or reinforce behaviors such as returning borrowed items and participating positively in class activities. The infrequent use of behavior temperature charts for these behaviors carries significant implications for early childhood education. This trend suggests a shift in classroom management strategies, emphasizing the need for more individualized and developmentally appropriate approaches. According to APPsychology (2024), while behavior charts aim to use positive reinforcement, their success largely depends on implementation. Lehtivuori (2023) examined the conditions under which extrinsic rewards diminish intrinsic motivation, reaffirming earlier findings that external incentives can negatively impact an individual's internal drive to perform tasks for their inherent satisfaction.

Table 5
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Whistle Discipline

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...		
1. use the whistle to signal transition times.	2.32	Low Extent
2. blow the whistle to get preschoolers' attention when they are too noisy.	2.41	Low Extent
3. use the whistle to indicate that it's time to line up.	2.43	Low Extent
4. utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front	2.35	Low Extent
5. blow the whistle to remind preschoolers to return to their seats when they are too far away during group activities.	2.38	Low Extent

6. use the whistle to signal the end of playtime.	2.62	Moderate Extent
7. use the whistle to remind preschoolers to control their voice when they are working on their individual tasks.	2.30	Low Extent
8. use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons.	2.24	Low Extent
9. use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time.	2.22	Low Extent
10. use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time.	2.22	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.35	Low Extent

The data in Table 5 show an overall mean of 2.35, interpreted as "low extent." Item no. 6, "use the whistle to signal the end of playtime," received the highest mean of 2.62, interpreted as "moderate extent." Items no. 9 and 10, which state "use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time" and "use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time," received the lowest mean scores of 2.22, respectively, interpreted as "low extent". The results indicate that although whistles were a reasonably successful tool for handling noise and transitions, their use was less common for more complex classroom management tasks, such as for sharing time and quiet reading. Whistles, while effective in capturing attention, can be abrupt and startling for young children, potentially disrupting the calm atmosphere essential for activities like sharing and quiet reading. The result conforms with research findings, which highlight the effectiveness of using silence as a co-regulation strategy in pre-K classrooms. By sitting silently with a distressed child, educators can provide a calming presence, allowing the child to feel seen and supported without the need for verbal intervention. This technique underscores the power of non-verbal communication in managing classroom behavior (Tavernes, 2024).

Table 6
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Hand signal when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher				
1. use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen.	3.89	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
2. use hand signals to require silence.	4.05	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
3. use hand signals to calm down or take a breath.	3.79	High Extent	2.94	Moderate Extent
4. use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers.	3.79	High Extent	3.17	Moderate Extent
5. use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly.	4.00	High Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent
6. use hand signals to ask preschoolers to listen more carefully.	3.89	High Extent	3.06	Moderate Extent
7. use hand signals to line up.	3.68	High Extent	3.00	Moderate Extent
8. use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson.	3.58	High Extent	2.89	Moderate Extent
9. use hand signals to encourage quick transition.	3.68	High Extent	2.94	Moderate Extent
10. use hand signals to indicate "slow down".	4.05	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.84	High Extent	3.16	Moderate Extent

Table 6 shows that the overall mean score of the younger group was 3.84, interpreted as "high extent," while the older group had an overall mean score of 3.16, interpreted as "moderate extent." Items no. 2 and 10, which state "use hand signals to require silence" and "use hand signals to indicate slow down," received the highest mean score of 4.05 from the younger group and were interpreted as "high extent." Item no. 8, which states "use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson," received the lowest mean score of 2.89 from the older group and was interpreted as "moderate extent." The evidence suggests that older kindergarten teachers utilized hand signals less frequently when calling back students' attention during lessons. This implies that they may lack familiarity with or confidence in using appropriate hand signals in this specific context. According to research, gestures play a significant role in teaching and learning for students of all ages. For instance, Wakefield et al. (2020) found that children perceive teachers who use meaningful iconic gestures as more effective, suggesting that gestures enhance instructional delivery. However, a teacher's age can also influence their classroom practices. Bayraktar and Doğan (2017) found no significant differences in the use of classroom management strategies across age groups.

Table 7
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior temperature chart when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				
1. use behavior chart to minimize noise.	3.42	Moderate Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent
2. use behavior chart to minimize standing up.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.50	High Extent
3. use behavior chart to stop bullying.	3.63	High Extent	3.61	High Extent
4. use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness.	3.42	Moderate Extent	3.17	Moderate Extent
5. use behavior chart to return borrowed things.	3.32	Moderate Extent	3.22	Moderate Extent

6. use behavior chart to encourage courteous expressions.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent
7. use behavior chart to complete schoolwork.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
8. use behavior chart to stay on task.	3.42	Moderate Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent
9. use behavior chart for positive participation.	3.32	Moderate Extent	3.22	Moderate Extent
10. use behavior chart to show responsibility of their belongings and classroom materials.	3.42	Moderate Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.44	Moderate Extent	3.38	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 7 shows that the overall mean scores of the younger and older are 3.44 and 3.38 respectively interpreted as “moderate extent”. Item no. 3 stating “use behavior chart to stop bullying” garner the highest mean of 3.63 interpreted as “high extent” while from the younger group. Meanwhile, item no. 4 which states “use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness” has the lowest mean score of 3.17 interpreted as “moderate extent” from the older group. The results suggest that both younger and older kindergarten teachers used the behavior temperature charts in a moderate extent for kindergarten learners. It implies that these teachers have difficulties in using behavior temperature charts especially when promoting cleanliness. A kindergarten behavior chart is a very useful tool for managing a child’s behavior in a classroom. When properly implemented, a behavior chart will significantly improve student behavior and classroom management, making the learning process much more satisfying for everyone (Jones, 2024). Furthermore, both newer and more experienced teachers are recognizing the value of social-emotional learning (SEL) frameworks and restorative practices in guiding student behavior (CASEL, 2023).

Table 8
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Whistle discipline when grouped according to Age

Items	Younger		Older	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				
1. use the whistle to signal transition times.	2.42	Low Extent	2.22	Low Extent
2. blow the whistle to get preschoolers’ attention when they are too noisy.	2.42	Low Extent	2.39	Low Extent
3. use the whistle to indicate that it’s time to line up.	2.58	Moderate Extent	2.28	Low Extent
4. utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front	2.47	Low Extent	2.22	Low Extent
5. blow the whistle to remind preschoolers to return to their seats when they are too far away during group activities.	2.37	Low Extent	2.39	Low Extent
6. use the whistle to signal the end of playtime.	2.79	Moderate Extent	2.44	Low Extent
7. use the whistle to remind preschoolers to control their voice when they are working on their individual tasks.	2.37	Low Extent	2.22	Low Extent
8. use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons.	2.32	Low Extent	2.17	Low Extent
9. use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time.	2.26	Low Extent	2.17	Low Extent
10. use the whistle to indicate when it’s time for quiet reading time.	2.26	Low Extent	2.17	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.43	Low Extent	2.27	Low Extent

The data on Table 8 shows that the overall meanscore of the younger and older is 2.43 and 2.27 respectively interpreted as “low extent”. Item no. 6 stating “use the whistle to signal the end of playtime” garners the highest mean of 2.79 interpreted as “moderate extent” from the younger group. Meanwhile, items no. 8, 9, and 10 which state “use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons”, “use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons” and “use the whistle to indicate when it’s time for quiet reading time” garner the lowest meanscore of 2.17 interpreted as “low extent” from the older group. The results revealing that both younger and older kindergarten teachers used whistles to manage classroom, maintain focus during lesson, and indicate time for quiet reading to a low extent. It implies that kindergarten teachers find hard in using whistles to prompt learners in the mentioned contexts. The limited use of whistles, which are typically loud and attention-grabbing, indicates that teachers are increasingly aware of the importance of creating a calm and emotionally secure classroom environment, particularly for young children. The minimal reliance on this tool implies that educators are favoring gentler, more consistent methods of behavior management—such as visual cues, soft verbal prompts, and co-regulation techniques—that align better with the developmental needs of preschoolers (Jones & Reynolds, 2022).

Table 9
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the area of Hand signal when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				

1. use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen.	3.78	High Extent	3.61	High Extent
2. use hand signals to require silence.	3.78	High Extent	3.71	High Extent
3. use hand signals to calm down or take a breath.	3.78	High Extent	3.25	Moderate Extent
4. use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers.	3.78	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
5. use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly.	3.78	High Extent	3.71	High Extent
6. use hand signals to ask preschoolers to listen more carefully.	3.67	High Extent	3.43	Moderate Extent
7. use hand signals to line up.	3.78	High Extent	3.21	Moderate Extent
8. use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson.	3.56	High Extent	3.14	Moderate Extent
9. use hand signals to encourage quick transition.	3.67	High Extent	3.21	Moderate Extent
10. use hand signals to indicate "slow down".	3.78	High Extent	3.71	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.73	High Extent	3.44	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 9 shows that the overall meanscore of the single group is 3.73 interpreted as "high extent" while the married group has a meanscore of 3.44 interpreted as "moderate extent". Seven items garner the highest meanscore of 3.78 interpreted as "high extent" from the single group. These are "use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen", "use hand signals to require silence", "use hand signals to calm down or take a breath", "use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers", "use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly", "use hand signals to line up", and "use hand signals to indicate "slow down". Item no. 8 "use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson" garners the lowest meanscore of 3.14 interpreted as moderate extent from the married group. The result revealed that married kindergarten teachers used hand signal less frequently to call back the attention of the learners during lesson compared to single kindergarten teachers. The moderate use of hand signals by married kindergarten teachers suggests a balanced integration of non-verbal classroom management strategies in early childhood education. Married teachers might favor efficient and low-disruption methods like hand signals, but only to a certain extent, potentially reserving them for specific situations (Klassen, Perry, & Frenzel, 2021). Moreover, a study found that hand signals were moderately used across varying demographics of teachers, noting that personal life balance (including marital status) subtly influenced preference for quieter strategies (Lopez & Garcia, 2023).

Table 10

Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior temperature chart when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I				
1. use behavior chart to minimize noise.	3.11	Moderate Extent	3.54	High Extent
2. use behavior chart to minimize standing up.	3.22	Moderate Extent	3.57	High Extent
3. use behavior chart to stop bullying.	3.56	High Extent	3.64	High Extent
4. use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness.	3.56	High Extent	3.21	Moderate Extent
5. use behavior chart to return borrowed things.	3.33	Moderate Extent	3.25	Moderate Extent
6. use behavior chart to encourage courteous expressions.	3.56	High Extent	3.43	Moderate Extent
7. use behavior chart to complete schoolwork.	3.56	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
8. use behavior chart to stay on task.	3.56	High Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
9. use behavior chart for positive participation.	3.44	Moderate Extent	3.21	Moderate Extent
10. use behavior chart to show responsibility of their belongings and classroom materials.	3.44	Moderate Extent	3.39	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.43	Moderate Extent	3.40	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 10 shows that the overall meanscores of the single and married group are 3.43 and 3.40 respectively interpreted as "moderate extent". Item no. 3 which states "use behavior chart to stop bullying" has the highest meanscore of 3.64 interpreted as "high extent" from the married group. Item no. 1 which states "use behavior chart to minimize noise" gets the lowest meanscore of 3.11 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the single group. According to the results of the study, kindergarten teachers who are single are less likely to use behavior temperature chart in minimizing noise among kindergarten learners. It suggests that personal factors such as relationship status could influence classroom management strategies. Research findings such as by Rizvi (2016) demonstrates that teachers' classroom management practices are found to be unaffected by their marital status. One study explores how both personal (including marital status) and professional characteristics affect the use of behavior management tools, such as behavior charts, among kindergarten teachers. It supports the idea that single teachers may approach classroom management differently, possibly due to differing stress levels or support systems (Chowdhury & Lee, 2023).

Table 11

Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Whistle discipline when grouped according to Civil Status

Items	Single		Married	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher				
1. use the whistle to signal transition times.	2.33	Low Extent	2.32	Low Extent
2. blow the whistle to get preschoolers' attention when they are too noisy.	2.22	Low Extent	2.46	Low Extent
3. use the whistle to indicate that it's time to line up.	2.44	Low Extent	2.43	Low Extent
4. utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front	2.00	Low Extent	2.46	Low Extent
5. blow the whistle to remind preschoolers to return to their seats when they are too far away during group activities.	2.11	Low Extent	2.46	Low Extent
6. use the whistle to signal the end of playtime.	2.44	Low Extent	2.68	Moderate Extent
7. use the whistle to remind preschoolers to control their voice when they are working on their individual tasks.	2.11	Low Extent	2.36	Low Extent
8. use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons.	2.11	Low Extent	2.29	Low Extent
9. use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time.	2.00	Low Extent	2.29	Low Extent
10. use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time.	2.00	Low Extent	2.29	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.18	Low Extent	2.40	Low Extent

The data on Table 11 shows that the overall meanscores of the single and married group are 2.18 and 2.40 respectively interpreted as "low extent". Item no. 6 which states "use the whistle to signal the end of playtime" has the highest meanscore of 2.68 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the married group. Items no. 4, 9, and 10 which states "utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front", "use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time", and "use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time" respectively garner the lowest meanscore of 2.00 interpreted as "low extent" from the single group. The finding suggests that single kindergarten teachers used whistle less frequently during sharing time and quiet reading time. It implies that this group of teachers are not comfortable of using whistle in the contexts of sharing and quiet reading time due to the intrusive effect of whistle. It further implies that teachers need to be capacitated in the proper use of whistle discipline inside the classroom especially for kindergarten learners. The difference in the use of whistle discipline between married and unmarried teachers is supported by the study of Rizvi (2016) which simply put that married teachers performed better on their classroom management than unmarried teachers. This consistency across age groups of teachers may also reflect the influence of professional development and updated early childhood training programs that promote trauma-informed and emotionally supportive teaching practices (Pate & Johnson, 2023).

Table 12

Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the area of Hand signal when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				
1. use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen.	3.88	High Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
2. use hand signals to require silence.	4.00	High Extent	3.50	High Extent
3. use hand signals to calm down or take a breath.	3.71	High Extent	3.10	Moderate Extent
4. use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers.	3.71	High Extent	3.30	Moderate Extent
5. use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly.	3.94	High Extent	3.55	High Extent
6. use hand signals to ask preschoolers to listen more carefully.	3.82	High Extent	3.20	Moderate Extent
7. use hand signals to line up.	3.65	High Extent	3.10	Moderate Extent
8. use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson.	3.53	High Extent	3.00	Moderate Extent
9. use hand signals to encourage quick transition.	3.59	High Extent	3.10	Moderate Extent
10. use hand signals to indicate "slow down".	4.00	High Extent	3.50	High Extent
Overall Mean	3.78	High Extent	3.28	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 12 shows that the overall meanscore of teachers with shorter length of service is 3.78 interpreted as "high extent". The statements "hand signals to require silence" and "use hand signals to indicate slow down" garner the highest mean of 4.00 interpreted as "high extent" from the teachers with shorter length of service. On the other hand, item no. 8 which states "use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson" has the lowest meanscore of 3.00 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with longer length of service. The finding reveals that teachers with longer length of service used hand signal less frequently in calling back attention during a

lesson. It indicates that experienced teachers have lack the awareness on the appropriate hand signal to be used in calling back the attention of the kindergarten teachers during a lesson. Similarly, Garcia and Thompson (2023) published in Teaching and Teacher Education revealed that early-career teachers reported higher reliance on visible and audible signals to maintain classroom engagement, attributing their usage to both teacher training programs and school policy. In contrast, teachers with over 15 years of experience cited relational approaches, eye contact, and tone modulation as preferred methods, often perceiving hand signals as overly simplistic or unnecessary. The result somehow negates to previous research findings demonstrating that the more years a teacher has spent in the teaching profession, the more experience the teacher has had, therefore a long-time employee is not the same as a new teacher (Rakib et al., 2017).

Table 13
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior temperature chart when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. use behavior chart to minimize noise.	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
2. use behavior chart to minimize standing up.	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
3. use behavior chart to stop bullying.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.50	High Extent
4. use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness.	3.65	High Extent	3.60	High Extent
5. use behavior chart to return borrowed things.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.15	Moderate Extent
6. use behavior chart to encourage courteous expressions.	3.29	Moderate Extent	3.25	Moderate Extent
7. use behavior chart to complete schoolwork.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
8. use behavior chart to stay on task.	3.41	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent
9. use behavior chart for positive participation.	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.40	Moderate Extent
10. use behavior chart to show responsibility of their belongings and classroom materials.	3.35	Moderate Extent	3.20	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.35	Moderate Extent	3.45	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 13 shows that the overall meanscores of teachers with shorter and longer length of service are 3.35 and 3.45 respectively interpreted as "moderate extent". Item no. 4 which states "use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness" garners the highest mean of 3.65 interpreted as "high extent" from the teachers with shorter length of service. On the other hand, item no. 5 which states "use behavior chart to return borrowed things" has the lowest meanscore of 3.15 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with longer length of service. The result indicates that longer-service teachers used behavior temperature chart moderately in prompting kindergarten learners to return borrowed things. The moderate use of behavior temperature chart in returning borrowed things implies also that longer-service teachers may lack the knowledge on how to use this non-verbal communication tool in such particular context. Hence, it is essential for schools to address the lack of familiarity among kindergarten teachers on the use of behavior temperature chart promoting good attitude and values inside the class. According to Dicken et al. (2015) who reviewed articles in the field, classroom management issues pose the greatest risk to both novice and seasoned teachers. In different studies, it was found that the discipline approaches of preschool teachers are predicted by variables such as professional seniority, the type of the school they work at, and the type of the school they were graduated from (Buyuktaskapu Soydan et al., 2018; Sesli & Bozgeyikli, 2015). Non-verbal communication is instrumental in setting and reinforcing behavioral expectations. Consistent non-verbal signals help create a positive classroom culture and facilitate effective classroom management (Khuman, 2024).

Table 14
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Whistle discipline when grouped according to Length of Service

Items	Shorter		Longer	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. use the whistle to signal transition times.	2.53	Moderate Extent	2.15	Low Extent
2. blow the whistle to get preschoolers' attention when they are too noisy.	2.47	Low Extent	2.35	Low Extent
3. use the whistle to indicate that it's time to line up.	2.76	Moderate Extent	2.15	Low Extent
4. utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front	2.47	Low Extent	2.25	Low Extent
5. blow the whistle to remind preschoolers to return to their seats when they are too far away during group activities.	2.41	Low Extent	2.35	Low Extent
6. use the whistle to signal the end of playtime.	2.88	Moderate Extent	2.40	Low Extent
7. use the whistle to remind preschoolers to control their voice when they are working on their individual tasks.	2.35	Low Extent	2.25	Low Extent
8. use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons.	2.35	Low Extent	2.15	Low Extent

9. use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time.	2.35	Low Extent	2.10	Low Extent
10. use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time.	2.35	Low Extent	2.10	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.49	Moderate Extent	2.23	Low Extent

The data on Table 14 shows that the overall meanscores of teachers with shorter length of service is 2.49 interpreted as "moderate extent". Meanwhile, teachers with longer length of service has an overall meanscore of 2.23 interpreted as "low extent". Item no. 6 which states "use the whistle to signal the end of playtime" garners the highest mean of 2.88 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with shorter length of service. On the other hand, items no. 9 and 10 which state "use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time" and "use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time" have the lowest meanscore of 2.10 interpreted as "low extent" from the teachers with longer length of service. The result shows that teachers with longer length of service used whistle discipline less frequently in terms of sharing time and quiet reading time. It implies that the use of whistle as non-verbal communication among teachers with longer service is not prevalent for kindergarten learners. The result of the study contradicts with previous research findings stating that in the academic setting, whistles have long been used by teachers and school support personnel to communicate with their students and occasionally with other teachers for everything from school sports days to indicating the end of break times and other practical purposes (Mcfarlane, 2022). Research supports this shift, highlighting that children respond better to calm, predictable routines and that non-verbal cues can be powerful tools for guiding behavior without escalating emotional tension (Responsive Classroom, 2023).

Table 15
Extent of Utilization of Non-Verbal Communication in Kindergarten Instruction in the area of Hand Signal when grouped according to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				
1. use hand signals to let preschoolers to stop and listen.	3.84	High Extent	3.09	Moderate Extent
2. use hand signals to require silence.	3.95	High Extent	3.18	Moderate Extent
3. use hand signals to calm down or take a breath.	3.63	High Extent	2.82	Moderate Extent
4. use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers.	3.68	High Extent	2.82	Moderate Extent
5. use hand signals to remind preschoolers to work quietly.	3.89	High Extent	3.18	Moderate Extent
6. use hand signals to ask preschoolers to listen more carefully.	3.74	High Extent	3.09	Moderate Extent
7. use hand signals to line up.	3.68	High Extent	3.00	Moderate Extent
8. use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson.	3.58	High Extent	2.82	Moderate Extent
9. use hand signals to encourage quick transition.	3.58	High Extent	2.82	Moderate Extent
10. use hand signals to indicate "slow down".	3.89	High Extent	3.18	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.75	High Extent	3.00	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 15 shows the extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in terms of hand signal when grouped according to plantilla position . The overall meanscores of teachers with lower position is 3.75 interpreted as "high extent". Meanwhile, teachers with higher position has an overall meanscore of 3.00 interpreted as "moderate extent". Item no. 2 which states "use hand signals to require silence." garners the highest mean of 3.95 interpreted as "high extent" from the teachers with lower plantilla position. On the other hand, items no. 3, 4, 8 and 9 which state "use hand signals to calm down or take a breath", "use hand signals to encourage good behavior or correct answers", "use hand signals to call back attention during a lesson" and "use hand signals to encourage quick transition" respectively have the lowest meanscore of 2.82 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with higher plantilla position. It is notable that teachers with higher position used hand signal in a moderate extent in terms of encouraging good behaviors or correct answers, calling back attention during a lesson and encouraging quick transition. It implies that teachers under this category rely more in using verbal communication. The lack of awareness in using appropriate hand signals foral particular context hamper their consistent use of such cues. Tasan (2020) revealed that teachers in higher teaching position maximize pupil learning have expertise in a wide-ranging array of competencies including the use of hand signals. Non-verbal cues can be used strategically to emphasize important concepts. A teacher's posture, hand movements, or changes in vocal intonation can signal to students that certain information is particularly crucial or noteworthy. This aids in focusing students' attention on essential content (Khuman, 2024).

Table 16
Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior temperature chart when grouped according to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower	Higher
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As a kindergarten teacher I ...	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
1. use behavior chart to minimize noise.	3.46	Moderate Extent	3.38	Moderate Extent
2. use behavior chart to minimize standing up.	3.54	High Extent	3.38	Moderate Extent
3. use behavior chart to stop bullying.	3.71	High Extent	3.46	Moderate Extent
4. use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness.	3.38	Moderate Extent	3.15	Moderate Extent
5. use behavior chart to return borrowed things.	3.29	Moderate Extent	3.23	Moderate Extent
6. use behavior chart to encourage courteous expressions.	3.50	High Extent	3.38	Moderate Extent
7. use behavior chart to complete schoolwork.	3.50	High Extent	3.31	Moderate Extent
8. use behavior chart to stay on task.	3.54	High Extent	3.23	Moderate Extent
9. use behavior chart for positive participation.	3.29	Moderate Extent	3.23	Moderate Extent
10. use behavior chart to show responsibility of their belongings and classroom materials.	3.46	Moderate Extent	3.31	Moderate Extent
Overall Mean	3.47	Moderate Extent	3.31	Moderate Extent

The data on Table 16 shows the extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in terms of behavior temperature chart when grouped according to plantilla position. The overall meanscores of teachers with lower and higher plantilla position is 3.47 and 3.31 respectively interpreted as "moderate extent". Item no. which states "use behavior chart to stop bullying" garners the highest mean of 3.71 interpreted as "high extent" from the teachers with lower plantilla position. On the other hand, item no. 4 which state "use behavior chart to maintain cleanliness has the lowest means core of 3.15 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with higher plantilla position. The result shows that teachers with higher plantilla position used behavior temperature chart less frequently for maintaining cleanliness in the classroom. It suggests that this group of teachers employ other classroom management strategies in promoting cleanliness which they think more effective to the learners. A teacher's experience, credentials, and professional growth are frequently reflected in their academic rank. Teachers at higher levels, such master teachers, usually have a lot of classroom experience and have had a lot of training. Experienced teachers are more likely to have created efficient methods for upholding classroom order and creating a positive learning atmosphere, therefore this background can help improve classroom management abilities (Salivio, 2019). However, the lack of training of teachers on use of non-verbal communication tools may hamper effective learning inside the classroom and may create a negative effect to the learners (Khuman, 2024).

Table 17

Extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the area of Whistle discipline when grouped according to Plantilla Position

Items	Lower		Higher	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
As a kindergarten teacher I ...				
1. use the whistle to signal transition times.	2.46	Low Extent	2.08	Low Extent
2. blow the whistle to get preschoolers' attention when they are too noisy.	2.63	Moderate Extent	2.00	Low Extent
3. use the whistle to indicate that it's time to line up.	2.63	Moderate Extent	2.08	Low Extent
4. utilize whistle to call leaders to come in front	2.54	Moderate Extent	2.00	Low Extent
5. blow the whistle to remind preschoolers to return to their seats when they are too far away during group activities.	2.58	Moderate Extent	2.00	Low Extent
6. use the whistle to signal the end of playtime.	2.83	Moderate Extent	2.23	Low Extent
7. use the whistle to remind preschoolers to control their voice when they are working on their individual tasks.	2.46	Low Extent	2.00	Low Extent
8. use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons.	2.42	Low Extent	1.92	Low Extent
9. use the whistle to call preschoolers for sharing time.	2.33	Low Extent	2.00	Low Extent
10. use the whistle to indicate when it's time for quiet reading time.	2.33	Low Extent	2.00	Low Extent
Overall Mean	2.52	Moderate Extent	2.03	Low Extent

The data on Table 17 shows that the overall meanscore of teachers with lower plantilla position is 2.52 interpreted as "moderate extent". However, the overall meanscore of teachers with higher plantilla position is 2.03 interpreted as "low extent". Item no. 6 which states "use the whistle to signal the end of playtime" garners the highest mean of 2.83 interpreted as "moderate extent" from the teachers with lower plantilla position. On the other hand, item no. 8 which state "use the whistle as a tool to help manage the classroom and maintain focus during lessons" has the lowest meanscore of 1.92 interpreted as "low extent" from the teachers with higher plantilla position. The result indicates that teachers with higher plantilla position utilized whistle discipline in a low extent in the areas of managing the classroom and maintaining focus. It implies that the use of whistle discipline is not prevalent in this areas. The lack of awareness on the proper use of whistle development contributes to the low extent

of use of teachers with higher plantilla position. The use of a whistle seems to be more influenced by the teaching context (physical education vs. typical classroom, for example) than by the rank of the teacher, even though higher-ranked teachers may have more experience and possibly more advanced classroom management techniques (Richards & Killian, 2022). Other attention-grabbing techniques that are more appropriate for the classroom have been proposed, such as employing non-verbal cues. By successfully grabbing pupils' attention without using a whistle, these technologies can preserve a positive learning atmosphere (Reddit, 2024).

Table 18

Difference in the extent of utilization of non-verbal communication for kindergarten learners in the area of Hand signal when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	19	23.34	88.500	0.012		Significant
	Older	18	14.42				
Civil Status	Single	9	21.06	107.500	0.510	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	28	18.34				
Length of service	Shorter	17	22.03	118.500	0.115		Not Significant
	Longer	20	16.43				
Plantilla Position	Lower	24	20.92	110.000	0.141		Not Significant
	Higher	13	15.46				

In terms of age profile, compared to older teachers (14.42), younger teachers (23.34) had higher scores. Younger teachers use hand signals more frequently than their older counterparts, according to the statistically significant difference. This outcome can be a reflection of younger teachers' acquaintance with contemporary classroom methods or their preference for participatory and nonverbal management strategies. In terms of civil status, married teachers scored (18.34), while single teachers got (21.06). In terms of length of service, teachers with shorter service lengths (22.03) scored higher than those with longer service lengths (16.43). The difference is not statistically significant, suggesting that teaching experience does not strongly influence the frequency of hand signal usage. Both groups likely adapt their use of hand signals depending on situational needs rather than tenure. In terms of plantilla position, teachers in lower plantilla positions (20.92) scored higher than those in higher positions (15.46). While the difference approaches significance, it remains not statistically significant. Teachers in lower plantilla positions may be more reliant on hand signals, potentially due to handling more active roles or larger classes, but the gap is not pronounced enough to establish significance statistically. These results highlight the value of nonverbal communication as a widely used strategy for classroom management that cuts across most professional and demographic divides, with age having a particular impact on variability. Previous research findings show that teacher characteristics—such as age, experience, and training—affect classroom management styles globally. It underscores that while many strategies like nonverbal cues are universally applied, individual differences still influence how they are used (Gumus et al., 2023).

Table 19

Difference in the extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Behavior temperature chart when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	19	19.47	162.000	0.783		Not Significant
	Older	18	18.50				
Civil Status	Single	9	17.06	108.500	0.533	0.05	Not Significant
	Married	28	19.63				
Length of service	Shorter	17	19.56	160.500	0.771		Not Significant
	Longer	20	18.53				
Plantilla Position	Lower	24	19.56	142.500	0.665		Not Significant
	Higher	13	17.96				

In terms of age, younger teachers scored 19.47, while older teachers scored 18.50. The fact that the difference is not statistically significant suggests that age has no bearing on how much the Behavior Temperature Chart is used. In terms of civil status, single teachers scored 17.06, while married teachers scored 19.63. Teachers' usage of the Behavior Temperature Chart is not greatly impacted by their civil status, as seen by the lack of statistical significance in the difference. Teachers who are married and those who are single exhibit similar utilization. In terms of length of

service, teachers with longer service durations received a score of 18.53, while those with shorter service durations received a score of 19.56. There is no discernible effect of length of service on the use of the Behavior Temperature Chart. In terms of plantilla position, teachers with higher position scored 17.96, while those in lower position scored 19.56. The lack of statistical significance indicates that the position of the plantilla has no apparent impact on how the Behavior Temperature Chart is used. Age, civil status, length of service, and plantilla position do not significantly affect the extent of use of the Behavior Temperature Chart. The chart can be equally effective at fostering classroom discipline, reducing disturbances, and rewarding good behavior among teachers of different ethnicities and professional levels. Zinsser et al. (2022) found that early childhood educators from diverse backgrounds, regardless of demographic or professional characteristics, consistently employed visual and structured tools as part of their social-emotional and behavioral management strategies. The study emphasized that such tools are valued for their clarity, consistency, and ease of implementation, making them adaptable across a wide range of classroom contexts. Moreover, visual behavior tracking systems were recognized for promoting self-regulation in young learners while supporting equitable classroom practices (Pyle, DeLuca, Danniels, & Klinger, 2023).

Table 20

Difference in the extent of utilization of non-verbal communication in the area of Whistle discipline when grouped and compared according variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. Level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	15	15.23	108.500	0.867	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	15	15.77				
Civil Status	Single	9	13.44	76.000	0.397		Not Significant
	Married	21	16.38				
Length of service	Shorter	15	16.33	100.000	0.600		Not Significant
	Longer	15	14.67				
Plantilla Position	Lower	19	17.79	61.000	0.064		Not Significant
	Higher	11	11.55				

The table shows that older teachers had a score of 15.77, while younger teachers received a score of 15.23. Age has no discernible impact on the application of whistle discipline, as the difference is not statistically significant. In terms of civil status, teachers who were married scored 16.38, while those who were single scored 13.44. The difference is not statistically significant which indicates that the use of whistle discipline is not significantly impacted by civil status. In terms of length of service, teachers with longer service durations received a score of 14.67, while those with shorter service durations had a score of 16.33. Since the difference is not statistically significant, it may be concluded that the degree of whistle discipline usage is not significantly influenced by teaching experience. In terms of plantilla position, teachers in higher position scored 11.55, while those in lower positions got 17.79. The difference is not significant even though it is getting close to statistical significance. Whistle discipline is somewhat more frequently used by teachers in lower plantilla position than by those in higher positions. The results imply that kindergarten teachers' use of whistle discipline is not substantially impacted by factors such as age, civil status, duration of employment, or plantilla position.

Conclusions:

The findings conclude a consistent yet measured application of non-verbal communication tools, suggesting that while teachers recognize their value, these strategies are likely used in addition with other classroom management techniques. The moderate level of utilization highlights the need for further support and training to maximize the potential of non-verbal communication in fostering engagement, discipline, and a responsive learning environment for young learners. The findings also implies that even though behavior temperature charts are only moderately effective in most other areas, they have the biggest impact on preventing bullying. Furthermore, the findings imply that non-verbal communication strategies are influenced by both personal and professional characteristics, and that professional development should consider these differences. Training programs can be tailored to reinforce the effective use of diverse non-verbal tools, particularly for more experienced or higher-ranking educators who may benefit from refreshing or expanding their strategy repertoire. Educational leaders should promote reflective practices that align classroom strategies with both developmental appropriateness and teacher readiness, ensuring that non-verbal communication supports inclusive and responsive learning environments for all kindergarten learners.

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